

Purchase Decisions on Rockland Bogor Convection T-Shirts

Baby Panca Masayu¹, Lucky Hikmat Maulana², Yulianingsih^{3*}, Titiek Tjahja Andari⁴

Juanda Bogor University

Corresponding Author: Yulianingsih yulianingsih@unida.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Perception Price, Promotion, Purchase Decision

Received : 21, August

Revised : 22, September

Accepted: 30, October

©2023 Masayu, Maulana, Yulianingsih, Andari: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze and identify the effect of price perceptions and promotions simultaneously or partially on purchasing decisions of Rockland Screen Printing Convection T-Shirts. Questionnaires were distributed to 60 respondents using purposive sampling technique with the following criteria; 1) consumers have purchased Rockland Screen Printing products at least 2 times, 2) consumers are at least 17 years old. Data collection was carried out through a questionnaire. The analytical method uses descriptive and verification methods through multiple correlation, multiple regression, coefficient of determination, F test and t test. The results showed that the perceived price and promotion variabls simultaneously or partially had a positive and significant effect on the purchasing decision of the Rockland Screen Printing Convection T-Shirt.

INTRODUCTION

Competition in the business world is getting tougher, becoming a challenge and threat for business people. One type of business that has quite tight competition is fashion T-shirts. This is indicated by the large number of similar companies offering their products through quite aggressive promotions at competitive prices so that consumers become selective in determining their clothing style. The company's accuracy in selecting marketing strategies will provide support to influence consumers in making purchasing decisions.

Rockland Screen Printing is a company in the city of Bogor that operates in the convection sector providing screen printing services such as T-shirts, pants, and bags and also accepting orders for clothes needed by schools/educational institutions.

This research was conducted only on T-Shirt sales because based on company data sales in 2022 will only reach 85%. The failure to achieve the company's target was caused by several factors, including a decrease in purchasing decisions, which was thought to be caused by pricing that did not meet consumer expectations and promotions carried out by the company that was not optimal.

To determine the decline in purchasing decisions, observations were made by comparing prices with similar products from main competitors. The observation results show that the T-shirt prices set by Rockland are more expensive than the prices set by its competitors. This is because the type of shirt material and type of screen printing used are of good quality so the price set is slightly more expensive than its main competitors. According to Daryanto (2016), price is the main factor that can influence a buyer's choice, price plays quite a role in determining consumer purchasing decisions.

As a company effort to attract buyers' attention, the company carries out various promotional activities. During the last 5 years from 2015-2022, the company has carried out a promotional mix that includes advertising, sales promotion, public relations, direct marketing and personal selling. However, this has not been able to improve consumer purchasing decisions.

The aims of this research are:

1. To find out consumer responses regarding price perceptions, promotions and T-shirt purchasing decisions at Rockland convection.
2. To find out and analyze perceptions of price and promotion simultaneously on T-shirt purchasing decisions at the Rockland convection.
3. To find out and partially analyze price and promotion perceptions of T-shirt purchasing decisions at the Rockland Convection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Management

According to Simamora (2016), management is the science of managing and utilizing human resources with other supporting resources to carry out processes efficiently and effectively to achieve predetermined goals.

Understanding Marketing

Kotler and Keller (2016) state that marketing is a social and managerial activity, either by individuals or groups, to get things they want or need by creating, offering or exchanging products that have value with other parties which can improve marketing product.

Understanding Marketing Management

According to Tjiptono (2016), marketing management is a system structure of a business activity that consists of planning, determining and distributing services, product statements or ideas to provide satisfaction to targets or target markets to achieve organizational goals.

Marketing Management Functions

1. Purchasing function (buying): This function is the activity of looking for sellers and then getting feedback from sales.
2. Sales function (selling): This function includes activities offering products to potential buyers.
3. Transportation function: Is the process of distributing or moving goods to another place.
4. Warehousing or storage function: Product storage functions as inventory and to avoid the risk of other damage.
5. Information function: This function is to search for and conclude information regarding sales related to goods, prices according to the target or target market, and overall market conditions related to the product in question.

Understanding Marketing Mix

Four marketing mix variables according to Tjiptono (2016:126-128), namely:

1. Products are services or goods that a company provides to the market.
2. Price is the amount of money value of a product that buyers must pay.
3. Place includes distribution channels that perform logistical functions for consumption.
4. Promotion means the activity of conveying product benefits and persuading customers.

Marketing Strategy

Marketing decisions consist of 4 parts, including product strategy, price, distribution and promotion. The interrelationship of these 4 strategies will build something called a marketing mix, which aims to determine the marketing success of a company's products and is aimed at satisfying market segments (Swastha, 2014: 192).

Marketing Mix

Alma (2012) states that the marketing mix is a mixed strategy that companies use for marketing strategies with good collaboration to provide significant positive results and impacts for the company.

Price Perception

1. Understanding Price

Kotler and Armstrong (2014) argue that price is the value of a product or service for the power used in a company's services and products. The price of a product is determined not only based on production costs but also on other

factors such as the level of demand for the product in question, the level of competition, and consumer perceptions of the product.

2. Understanding Price Perception

Peter and Olson (2016) argue that price perception is related to price information for goods and services which has meaning for buyers. This can be interpreted as price perception which influences buyers in determining prices based on the quality of goods or services.

3. Price Perception Indicator

Kotler and Armstrong (2014) argue that 4 measures identify price perceptions, namely as follows:

a. Keterjangkauan harga

That is, the products, services and goods offered by the company have a value that is appropriate to the consumer's condition. In a product, there are different prices in one brand, some are cheap and some are expensive. By determining the selling price of the product, many consumers buy it.

b. Price compliance with product quality.

Price is an indicator of quality for most consumers because a high price indicates the quality of the product. Consumers assume that expensive products have guaranteed quality and provide satisfaction.

c. Matching Price with Benefits

The buyer's decision regarding product ownership will be determined if it is felt that the intended product has benefits commensurate with the amount of money to get the product. If the benefits of the product are felt to be not the same or less than the buyer's expenditure, the buyer will consider repurchasing the product.

d. Price competitiveness.

Buyers often compare the prices of one product with another to match the buyer's ability to obtain the product.

Promotion

1. Definition of Promotion

Swastha (2014) said that promotion is the one-way distribution of data from an organization to create exchanges in marketing. According to Daryanto (2016:94), promotion is one-way information or invitation to create sales and purchase transactions.

2. Promotion Indicator

In this research, the indicators used are indicators according to Kotler & Keller (2016:272), the following are promotion indicators:

a. Promotional Messages are a measure of the goodness and badness of promotional messages to the target market.

b. Promotional Media is a means used as an intermediary for promotional activities by the company.

c. Promotion Time is whether or not the promotion is carried out by the company.

Buying decision

1. Understanding Purchasing Decisions

That is the flow that starts with the buyer identifying the problem, looking for data about the product or brand then evaluating a related product whether it is good or not to use as a solution to the problem, then this flow or process will lead to a purchasing decision. (Tjiptono, 2016:21).

2. Purchase Decision Indicators

The author draws several indicators that are relevant to this research, namely as follows:

- a. Product Choice, companies must focus their attention on people who will be interested in a product and alternatives that buyers consider, such as types of product variants, product quality, and suitability of interests.
- b. Brand choice, a company must know how customers believe in a brand through popularity and trust.
- c. Time of purchase, buyers' beliefs are always different, such as purchasing every 3 or 6 months or even once a year.
- d. The number of purchases and fulfillment of buyers' product needs must be prepared by the company because each individual has a different willingness to buy.
- e. Payment methods, payment methods are carried out by technological developments which are also a factor in purchasing decisions.

Research Hypothesis

H1: Perceptions of price and promotion simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase T-shirts at the Rockland Convection.

H2: Price perception has a partially positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase T-shirts at the Rockland convection.

H3: Promotion has a partially positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase T-shirts at the Rockland convection.

METHODOLOGY

The research object includes price and promotion perceptions as independent variables and purchasing decisions as the dependent variable. This research is quantitative research, with descriptive and verification methods through survey methods. The research population is consumers who bought t-shirts at the Rockland convection in 2022. The sampling technique used purposive sampling. The criteria for respondents are:

1. Consumers who have purchased Rockland t-shirt products at least 3 times
2. Consumers who are mature enough to fill out the questionnaire, must be at least seventeen years old because they can make rational purchasing decisions.

Based on the criteria, 150 consumers were obtained as the population. Using the Notoatmodjo (2010) formula, the following sample size was obtained:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(d^2)}$$

Information:

n= Number of samples

N= Number of population

d2= confidence level / speed (0.1)

If all the variables above are adjusted to the Notoatmojo formula, then:

$$n = \frac{150}{1 + 150(0,1)^2} = 60$$

Based on the calculation results above, the number of samples (respondents) in this study was 60 consumers.

Instrument Testing Methods

Instrument testing was carried out through validity and reliability tests and all instruments on the price, promotion and purchasing decision variables were valid and reliable. Apart from that, classical assumption tests were carried out consisting of normality tests, multicollinearity tests and heteroscedasticity tests. Based on the results of the classical assumption test, the sample data is normally distributed, free from multicollinearity and there is no heteroscedasticity.

Data Analysis Method

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

According to Sinambela (2014), multiple linear regression discusses the relationship or influence of the dependent variable with two or more independent variables. The use of multiple linear regression analysis in this research is to find out whether price perceptions and promotions influence purchasing decisions at the Rockland Screen Printing Convection. To be able to analyze multiple regression, the following formula is used:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Information :

Y = attachment variable (purchase decision)

X₁ = Price perception

X₂ = Promotion

α = constant

β₁ = price perception regression coefficient

β₂ = promotion regression coefficient

e = other factors not studied

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

According to Ghozali (2014:286), the correlation coefficient is a number that shows the direction and strength of the relationship between 2 or more independent variables simultaneously and one dependent variable. This notation uses correlation or relationship between the variables tested in the research, as follows:

1. If $r = 0$ or close to 0, then the two variables have no relationship or they have a weak relationship.
2. If $r = +1$ or almost 1, then the two variables have a unidirectional and very strong relationship, meaning that an increase in X values will be followed by an increase in Y values, or vice versa.
3. If $r = -1$ or almost -1, it means that the two variables are related in opposite directions and are very strong, meaning that an increase in X values is followed by a decrease in Y values or vice versa.

Coefficient of Determination Analysis (R^2)

According to Priyatno (2013), analysis of the coefficient of determination is to determine the percentage contribution of the influence of the independent variables together. dependent variable. To calculate the coefficient of determination, you can use the following formula:

$$KD = r^2 \times 100\%$$

Information:

KD = Coefficient of Determination

R = Correlation Coefficient

Hypothesis Test

1. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

F Test Decision Criteria

- a. If F_{count} is smaller than F_{table} ($F_{count} \leq F_{table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 and H_a are rejected, meaning that price perceptions and promotions do not influence the decision to purchase T-shirts at the Rockland convection simultaneously.
- b. If the calculated F is greater than the F table ($F_{count} > F_{table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that simultaneously the perception of price and promotion does not influence the decision to purchase T-shirts at the Rockland convection.

2. Partial Test (t Test)

T-Test Decision Criteria

- a. For price perception, if the count is equal to or smaller than the table ($count \leq table$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, meaning that price perception does not have a positive and significant influence on partial purchasing decisions for Rockland Convection T-shirts. Meanwhile, if t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($t_{count} > t_{table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_a is accepted, meaning that partial price perception has a positive and significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland Screen Printing Convection T-shirts.
- b. For price perception, if the count is equal to or smaller than the table ($count \leq table$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, meaning that price perception does not have a positive and significant influence on partial purchasing decisions for Rockland Convection T-shirts. Meanwhile, if t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($t_{count} > t_{table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_a is accepted, meaning that partial price perception has a positive

and significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland Screen Printing Convection T-shirts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of processing the questionnaire are consumer responses to determine the influence of price perceptions and promotions on purchasing decisions for Konveksi Rokcland Bogor T-shirts. The consumer responses are as follows:

Table 1. Recapitulation of Consumer Responses Regarding Price Perceptions (X1)

No	Indikator	Skor	Kriteria	Inteprestasi
1	Affordability	3,49	Affordable	Consumers assess that the prices set by the company are affordable starting from IDR 125,000–IDR 150,000
2	Matching price to product quality	3,56	Affordable	Consumers provide an assessment that the price set is by the quality of the product. Consumers can choose the quality of materials they want according to their financial conditions.
3	Matching price to product quality	3,6	Affordable	Consumers assess that the price matches the benefits because it is comfortable when used and can absorb sweat
4	Price competitiveness	3,35	Quite Affordable	Consumers assess that the prices set by the company are quite competitive but a bit expensive when compared to competing brands
Average Score of Price Perception Variable		3,50	Affordable	The majority of consumers have the perception that Rockland product prices are affordable, have quality and benefits that match the price and have products that can compete.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2021

Based on table 1, the recapitulation of consumer response scores regarding price perception variables with indicators of price suitability to product quality, price affordability, price suitability to benefits and price competitiveness has an average score value of 3.50, which means that product price perception is included in the affordable category. The price suitability indicator based on benefits is the highest with a figure of 3.6, which means the value is in the affordable category. Meanwhile, the price competitiveness indicator is the lowest value, getting a figure of 3.35, which means that there are consumers who choose to buy Rockland products, but not all consumers feel the same way because there are still some consumers who think that the price of Rockland products is higher than similar products. from other companies.

This can be a consideration for Rockland, Rockland needs to make price adjustments to be able to compete with other producers and be able to meet the company's targets. The company's methods include giving discounts to consumers who have subscribed, giving discounts when purchasing more than one item code and providing special prices on national holidays or at the end of the year as well as showing the differences or advantages between Rockland products and other products. In this way, consumers decide to purchase products from Rockland Screen Printing.

The following is a recapitulation of the overall score of respondents' responses to the promotion variable (X2) presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Recapitulation of Consumer Responses Regarding Promotions (X2)

No	Indicator	Score	criteria	Interpretation
1	Promotional Messages	3,24	Pretty Good	The information conveyed is sometimes unclear, thus influencing decisions to purchase Rockland products.
2	Media promotion	3,73	Good	Social media makes it easier for consumers to get information about the latest promotions.
3	Promotion time	3,27	Pretty Good	The majority of consumers buy Rockland T-shirts because they often see advertisements on social media, but the promotional period is quite short
Promotion Variable Average Score		3,41	Good	Consumers make purchases because they get information through social media which contains information about products on an ongoing basis.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2021

Based on Table 2, the recapitulation of respondents' response scores regarding promotional variables with indicators of promotional messages, promotional media and promotional time has an average score of 3.41, which means it is included in the good category. This shows that the Rockland Screen Printing convection promotion informs buyers about new products, brand benefits, and discounts at certain sessions to increase interest in buying Rockland products or t-shirts.

The promotional media indicator has the highest score of 3.73 which is included in the good category. Meanwhile, the promotional message indicator has the lowest value of 3.24, which is included in the quite good category, which means that some consumers have the perception that the information and message content conveyed cannot be digested/understood by consumers. The solution is an effort to increase the effectiveness of delivering information regularly, and clearly and attracting consumers to understand the content of the message. Rockland can utilize applications or media that provide space to display product advertisements that can encourage consumers to make purchases such as social media (Instagram, Facebook, Tiktok, Youtube) and e-commerce platforms such as Shoppe, Lazada, Tokopedia, blibli.com or others that can encourage consumers to decide to purchase Rockland products.

The following is a recapitulation of the overall score of responses from the Purchasing Decision variable (Y) which is described in table 3 below as follows:

Table 3. Recapitulation of Consumer Responses Regarding Purchasing Decision Variables (Y)

No	Indicator	Score	criteria	Interpretation
1	Product selection	3,8	High	Rockland has various types of products, and attractive designs and provides custom t-shirts.
2	Brand choice	3,12	High enough	Rockland brand T-shirts are a trusted brand seen from the uniqueness of the products sold in terms of color, motif, design or materials used.
3	Purchase	3,01	High	Consumers make purchases irregularly but during

	time		Enough	promotions or certain times.
4	Purchase amount	3,55	High	Consumers buy Rockland T-shirts when there are promotions or discounts and according to consumer needs.
5	Payment method	3,55	High	Rockland provides cash and non-cash payment methods so that consumers can make payments according to their wishes.
	Average Score of Purchase Decision Variables	3,41	Tinggi	Purchasing decisions at Rockland are high considering that with a variety of product choices with priority brands, consumers buy according to their desires and needs, especially at certain times or during product discounts using cash and non-cash payment methods.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2021

Based on table 3, a recapitulation of respondents' response scores on purchasing decisions with indicators of brand choice, product choice, time of purchase, and number of purchases with an average score of 3.41 which is included in the high criteria. As for the product choice indicator, the highest score is 3.8, which means the score is in the high category. Meanwhile, the purchase time indicator is the lowest value, getting a figure of 3.01, which means the value is in the quite high category.

This shows that not all consumers make purchases regularly, but some consumers prefer to make purchases during discounts or promotions. It would be better if Rockland could make discount provisions that are interconnected with previous product purchases so that consumers are interested in making regular purchasing decisions.

Data Analysis Results

Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5,673	2,058		2,757	,008
	Price Perception	,387	,121	,397	3,194	,002
	Promotion	,717	,169	,527	4,247	,000

a. Dependent variabel: Buying Decision

Source: Data processing output with SPSS 22, 2021

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the values of the regression equation model are as follows.

$$Y = 5.673 + 0,387 X_1 + 0,717 X_2$$

The interpretation of the results of the multiple linear regression test above is as follows:

1. The constant value is positive at 5.673, which means that when the price perception variable (X1) and promotion variable (X2) do not change, the decision variable to purchase Rockland t-shirt products does not change.

2. The β_1 coefficient value of the price perception variable has a positive multiple regression coefficient of 0.387, meaning that a better assessment of product price perceptions at Rockland Convection will increase purchasing decisions.
3. The coefficient value β_2 on the promotion variable has a positive multiple regression coefficient of 0.717, meaning that if the promotion variable (X2) is increased it will increase the level of purchasing decisions.

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

The coefficient values are explained in Table 5 below:

Table 5. Multiple Correlation Coefficient

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.897 ^a	.805	.798	3,066
a. Predictors: (Constant), promotion, price perception				
b. Dependent variabel: Buying Decision				

Source: Data processing output with SPSS 22, 2021

Based on Table 5. Above, it is known that the R-value is 0.897, which indicates that the R-value (0.897) is in the R interval (0.80 – 1.000) with a very strong degree of relationship strength, so the two variables have a unidirectional and very strong relationship. strong relationship between the price perception variable (X1) and the promotion variable (X2) on the purchasing decision variable.

This is by the correlation between the variables tested in the research, where if $r = 1$ or close to 1, then the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional and very strong, meaning that when variable X experiences an increase it will be followed by an increase in the value of variable Y. Good price perception (X1) and better promotion (X2) will directly result in increasing purchasing decisions (Y) so that sales can reach targets so that company goals can be achieved.

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Testing the coefficient of determination aims to determine the level of influence of the Price Perception variable (X1), and the Promotion variable (X2) simultaneously on the increase or decrease in the Purchase Decision variable (dependent). The results of data processing using SPSS version 22 are shown in Table 6. Below:

Table 6. Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.897 ^a	.805	.798	3,066
a. Predictors: (Constant), promotion, price perception				
b. Dependent variabel: Buying Decision				

Source: Data processing output with SPSS 22, 2021

Based on Table 6 above, it is known that the magnitude of determination (R2) or the contribution of the influence of price perception (X1) and promotion (X2) on the purchase decision (Y) of Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen

Printing convection in Megamendung, Bogor Regency can be seen in the R Square value. Based on the calculation results of the R square value with the number 0.805 or 80.5%, the influence of the Price Perception (X1) and Promotion (X2) variables on Purchasing Decisions (Y) is 80.5%, while the remaining 19.5% is based on other influencing factors and not included in this research such as products, marketing channels, and consumer preferences (Kotler and Keller, 2016: 165).

1. Influence of Price Perception (X1) on Purchasing Decisions.

To determine whether or not there is an influence of price perception on purchasing decisions, the hypothesis will be statistically tested, namely:

- Ho: $\beta_1 = 0$:** Price perception does not have a positive or partially significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection.
- Ha: $\beta_1 \neq 0$:** Price perceptions have a positive and significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection.

Price perception (X1) with a t value of 3.194 is greater than the t-table (3.194 > 2.002) and a significant level of 0.002 < 0.05 means that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. This condition means that price perceptions partially have a positive and significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection. The results of the one-party test for the price perception variable can be seen in the following picture:

Figure 1. Variable T-Test Results

Source: Data processed, 2021

Based on Figure 1, the price perception variable obtains a count value of 3.194 and the table value for $\alpha=0.5$ degrees of freedom 60-2-1 = 57 is 2.002, so count > table (3.194 > 2.002) so Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected, meaning price perception has a significant and positive influence on purchasing decisions partially. As research by Ferdyanto (2020) states positive price perceptions influence purchasing decisions.

2. Effect of Promotion (X2) on Purchasing Decisions (Y)

To determine whether or not there is an influence of promotional variables on purchasing decisions, the following hypothesis will be statistically tested:

- Ho: $\beta_1 = 0$:** Promotions do not have a positive and significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection partially.
- Ha: $\beta_1 \neq 0$:** Promotions have a positive and significant influence on the decision to purchase Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection.

The partial test results obtained a count value for the promotion of 4.247, so $\text{count} > t_{\text{table}}$ or $4.247 > 2.002$ based on significance, namely 0, <0.05. This means that H_0 is rejected then H_a is accepted. This condition means that promotions primarily influence purchasing decisions. Rockland t-shirts at Rockland Screen Printing convey positively and significantly. The results of the one-party test for the promotion variable can be seen in the following picture:

Figure 2. Variable T Test Results

Sumber: Data processed, 2021

Berdasarkan Gambar 2 variabel promosi memperoleh nilai thitung sebesar 4,247 dan nilai ttabel untuk $\alpha=0,5$ derajat kebebasan $60-2-1 = 57$ sebesar 2.002 maka $t_{\text{hitung}} > t_{\text{tabel}}$ ($4,247 > 2,002$) sehingga H_a diterima dan H_0 ditolak, artinya promosi memengaruhi keputusan pembelian secara parsial ddengan positif dan signifikan, sesuai dengan Purbiyanto (2021) menyatakan bahwa variabel promosi positif dan signifikan pada keputusan pembelian.

Dari hasil uji tersebut, dibuat rekapitulasi pengujian secara parsial yaitu variabel Persepsi harga dan Promosi sebagai berikut:

Table 7 Partial Test Recapitulation

No	Variabel	T _{count}	t _{table}	Sig.	Conclusion
1	Price Perception	3,194	2,002	0,002	Price Perception (X1) has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions (Y)
2	Promotion	4,247	2,002	0,000	Promotion (X2) has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions (Y)

Sourcer: Data processed, 2021

It can be concluded from Table 7 that Promotion (X2) has a greater influence on purchasing decisions (Y) for Rockland Bogor T-shirts than the influence of price perception (X1). This shows that consumers assess that the promotional activities carried out by Rockland have been well received, with the various promotional activities carried out, expanding product information clearly and attractively with a count of 4.247.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the description above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Consumer responses to price perception variables, promotion variables and purchasing decision variables:

- a. The average consumer assessment of price perception is in the cheap criteria, the item price suitability for benefits is the highest assessment with a cheap interpretation and the lowest assessment item is price competitiveness with the interpretation quite cheap
 - b. The average consumer assessment of promotions is in the good criteria, promotional media items are the highest rated with a good interpretation and the lowest rated items are promotional messages with a fairly good interpretation.
 - c. The average consumer score on purchasing decisions is at high criteria, the product choice item is the highest assessment with a cheap interpretation and the lowest assessment item is purchase time with a quite high interpretation
2. There is a significant and positive influence simultaneously between the price perception variable and the promotion variable on the decision variable to purchase Rockland T-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection.
 3. The price perception variable and the promotion variable have an influence on the purchasing decision variable for Rockland T-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection simultaneously as follows:
 - a. The price perception variable (X1) influences the purchasing decision variable (Y) of Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection positively and is also partially significant.
 - b. The promotional variable (X2) influences the purchasing decision (Y) of Rockland t-shirts at the Rockland Screen Printing convection positively and is also partially significant.

The description of the research conclusions above provides a suggestion put forward by the researcher as follows:

1. For the price perception variable with the price competitiveness indicator, the statement item with the lowest value is the statement "cheap product prices," the results show that according to consumers the price of Rockland t-shirts is relatively high compared to the prices of other convection products. This can be used as an evaluation by the company so that it can provide clearer information regarding the factors determining the prices that will be offered to consumers. Apart from that, Rockland can provide discounts to consumers who have subscribed, provide discounts when purchasing more than one item code and provide special prices on big holidays such as Hari Raya or the end of the year.
2. For the promotion variable with the promotional message indicator, it has a statement item with the lowest value, namely the statement "the information conveyed can give consumers the confidence to buy Rockland products". This can be used as an evaluation to give consumers the confidence to buy Rockland products with clear information regarding the attributes, price, quality or benefits of the product. Apart from that, to increase promotions with social media such as Instagram, TikTok, and e-commerce platforms such as Shoppe, Lazada, Tokopedia, and blibli.com.

3. Divide the purchasing decision variable with the purchase time indicator and have the statement item "I buy Rockland T-Shirts regularly." This can be used as an evaluation, Rockland should be able to make discount provisions related to previous product purchases.

FURTHER RESEARCH

Future researchers can use this research as reference and reference material. It is recommended for future researchers to look for other variables related to purchasing decisions, for example, brand image variables, quality of production goods and product design so that they can get varied results and influence purchasing decisions involving many respondents to get more significant results and influence.

REFERENCES

- Alma, B. (2018). *Manajemen Pemasaran dan Pemasaran Jasa* (Cetakan 13 ed.). Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Amirullah. (2015). *Pengantar Manajemen*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- Ardyan, A. (2017). *Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Harga Produk Dan Promosi Produk terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Konveksi Recklezz*. Skripsi (S1) UPN Veteran Yogyakarta.
- Assael, H. (2016). *Perilaku Konsumen*. Jakarta: Binapura Aksara.
- Assauri, S. (2017). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Aziz, A. M., & Irjayanti, M. (2014). *Manajemen*. Bandung: Mardika Group.
- Daryanto. (2016). *Manajemen Pemasaran: Sari kuliah*. Bandung: Satu nusa.
- Dinawan. (2016). *Kualitas Produk: Alat Strategi yang Penting*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Esna Harahap, S. (2020). *Pengaruh Persepsi Harga dan Motivasi Konsumen Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Toko Mega Fashion Palembang*. S-1 Thesis, Universitas Tridianti Palembang. <http://repository.univ-tridianti.ac.id/id/eprint/2017>. Diakses pada 25 Agustus 2021
- Ferdyanto, S. (2020). *Pengaruh Persepsi Harga, Promosi dan Kualitas Layanan terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Studi Pada Perusahaan Ritel Dijakarta)*. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan*. Volume 5/No.3/,279-284. <http://journal.untar.ac.id/index.php/jmbk/article/view/11863>. Diakses pada 25 Agustus 2021
- Ghozali, I. (2014). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivaiate dengan Program SPSS*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit UNDIP.
- Husaini, U. (2014). *Manajemen Teori, Praktik, dan Riset*. Yogyakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Jamaludin, A., Zainul, A., & Kadarisman, H. (2015). *Pengaruh Promosi Online dan Persepsi Harga Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Survei pada Pelanggan Aryka Shop di Kota Malang)*. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*, 1-8. Diakses pada 25 Agustus 2021
- Keller, K. d. (2016). 165.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Manajemen Pemasaran Edisi 12 Jilid 1 & 2*. Jakarta: PT.Indeks.
- Kotler, P., Philip, & Amstrong, G. (2014). *Principles Of Marketing, 12 th. Edition Jllid 1 Terjemahan Bob Sabran*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Kurniawan, F. Y. (2017). *Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Harga, dan Kepercayaan Terhadap Proses Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Perusahaan Konveksi*

- Inglorious Industries di Kota Bandung. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 735-744. Diakses pada 25 Agustus 2021
- Kurtz, D. L. (2012). *Principle of Contemporary Marketing 14th Edition*. USA: Cengage Learning.
- Lupiyoadi, R. (2013). *Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa Edisi 3*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Morisan. (2016). *Periklanan Komunikasi Pemasaran Terpadu*. Jakarta: Ramdina Prakarsa.
- Peter, J., Paul, & Olson, J. C. (2016). *Perilaku Konsumen dan Strategi Pemasaran Edisi Sembilan Buku 2*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Priyatno, D. (2013). *Analisis Korelasi, Regresi, dan Multivariate dengan SPSS*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media.
- Purbiyanto, E. (2021). Pengaruh Persepsi Harga dan Promosi terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Air Minum Syekher Water. *Journal of Applied, Social and Education Studies*, 70-86. Diakses pada 25 Agustus 2021
- Rangkuni, F. (2016). *Riset Pemasaran*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Samosir, C. B., & K, B. P. (2015). Pengaruh Persepsi Harga dan Promosi terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Produk Enervon-C.
- Schiffman, Leon, & Kanuk, L. L. (2014). *Perilaku Konsumen*. Jakarta: Indeks.
- Shinta, A. (2016). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Malang: Universitas Brawijaya Press.
- Simamora, H. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT.Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Sinambela, L. P. (2014). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Srikinasih, m. &. (2018). Pengaruh Bauran Pemasaran Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Percetakan pada PT Balebat Dedikasi Prima Bogor. *jurnal visionida*, 4, 67-78.
- Sugiyono. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: PT.Alfabet.
- Sumiati, S., & Mujanah, S. (2018). Persepsi Kualitas Produk, Persepsi Harga dan Promosi terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Tas Sophie Paris pada Mahasiswa. *AMAR (Andalas Management Review)*.
- Tjitono, F. (2016). *Service, Quality & Satisfaction*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Violin, V., Mawardi, S., & Nasriani. (2021). Pengaruh Promosi, Persepsi Harga dan Distribusi Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Minuman Coca-Cola di Makassar. *Economics and Digital Business Review*, 205-213.
- Wicaksono, P. U., & Mudianto. (2017). Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Persepsi Harga, Promosi terhadap Citra Merek dan Minat Beli Sertadampaknya pada Keputusan Pembelian Kartu Perdanaxl Axiata Di Semarang. *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 1-11.
- Wulandari, N. (2021). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Citra Merek, Persepsi Harga, dan Promosi terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Studi Pada Pakaian Muslim Elzatta Semarang). *Undergraduate Thesis, Universitas Stikubank*.
- Yulianingsih. (2018). Hubungan Antara Kualitas Produk Dan Citra Merek Dengan Keputusan Pembelian Pada PT. Hyundai Mobil Indonesia Cabang Serpong-Tangerang. *Visionda*, 4(2), 23-37.
- _____, Kartini, T., & Kurniawan, D. (2020). Analisis Keputusan Pembelian Melalui Citra Merek dan Persepsi Harga. *Inovator*, 9(1), 8-16.